

MOVE3D - Software for Analyzing Human Motion

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Abstract

MOVE3D software was designed for use in the Department of Rehabilitation Medicine at the National Institutes of Health. The software uses data obtained from a 3D motion measurement system to provide quantitative analysis of human musculoskeletal motion including three-dimensional graphical displays. MOVE3D aids in the understanding of human motion disorders, leading to recommendations and improvements in clinical interventions. The software is designed for clinical flexibility and can be used to study a variety of motion disorders. Currently patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis and Post-Polio syndrome are among the populations being studied with MOVE3D. MOVE3D is also provided at no cost to motion analysis labs worldwide.

1 Introduction

The software entry, titled MOVE3D, is a three-dimensional motion analysis and computer graphics program for evaluating human musculoskeletal motion. The program uses input from a video based three-dimensional measurement system to quantify the kinematic and dynamic parameters which characterize human motion. The program input includes the three-dimensional locations of targets used to measure the motion of the anatomical segments, the three-dimensional ground reaction force vectors, and the anthropometric measures needed to create the anatomical model. The program output includes both kinematics and dynamic parameters. The kinematic parameters which can be evaluated include joint angular displacements, velocities and accelerations, as well as segmental translations, velocities and accelerations. Dynamic parameters which can be evaluated include the net forces, torques and powers generated at the anatomical joints.

MOVE3D was designed for use in the Department of Rehabilitation Medicine at the National Institutes of Health (NIH). Because the Department of Rehabilitation Medicine provides clinical and research support for several NIH Institutes it was necessary to design MOVE3D with the flexibility to analyze movement disorders for a wide variety of patient populations. Currently the software is being used to analyze the efficacy of forefoot surgery for rheumatoid arthritics. It is believed that this work will help produce interventions which can improve the ambulation capabilities of the patients suffering from this disease. MOVE3D

is also being used to study power generation of post-polio syndrome patients during walking. It is hypothesized that elevated power levels (relative to maximum power) produced by post-polio patients during ambulation will lead to premature deterioration of muscle strength. The software has also been used to research normal ankle-subtalar motion [1], gait adaptations in femoral neuropathy patients [2], and foot and ankle function in patients with rheumatoid arthritis [3]. Additionally, MOVE3D has been used clinically for such diverse applications as upper extremity prosthesis design, effects of lower extremity bracing in osteogenesis imperfecta children, and recommendations for intervention on a proteus syndrome patient.

2 Software Description

The MOVE3D software operates on three-dimensional coordinate data obtained from targets fixed to key anatomical landmarks. At least three targets must be fixed to each anatomical segment in order to measure its position and orientation. For dynamic evaluations, the vectoral composition of any external load applied to the subject, including ground reaction forces, must also be supplied.

During the operation of the software the file containing the targets coordinate and force data must be entered into the program. In addition, the targets must be assigned by number to their respective segments. The subject's body weight and segmental radii must also be supplied to allow the program to estimate the segments' inertial properties; geometric modeling is used for these estimates. The final input to the program is a data file from a stationary trial which creates a mapping of the targets to the segmental anatomy.

The available data analysis options include: 1) the angular displacement of any measured segment; 2) the angular velocity of any measured segment; 3) the angular acceleration of any measured segment; 4) the net joint forces at any or all joints along a measured limb; 5) the net moments at any joint along a measured limb; and 6) the net power generated at any joint along a measured limb. The angular motions analyzed through options 1, 2 or 3 may be computed relative to the stationary laboratory coordinate system (LCS) or relative to the body coordinate system (BCS) of any measured segment. The output for all options (except joint powers, a scalar quantity) may be expressed in either the BCS of any measured segment or in the LCS. The data is analyzed over a defined data inter-

val with the output written to ASCII formatted files. A plotting routine provides output displays which can be directed to the terminal screen or a hard copy device. MOVE3D also contains a graphics section to supply three-dimensional motion reconstruction (the geometric models used in the graphics are the same as the models used in the segmental inertial estimates). Figure 1 illustrates a three-dimensional graphics display for a subject undergoing a walking evaluation. In addition, graphical displays of the ground reaction force histories can also be obtained from the program (Figure 2). These displays, along with the analyzed data, can be used to isolate stability and propulsion problems in the movement impaired subject.

A recent addition to MOVE3D has been the capability to analyze changes in lower extremity muscle lines of action during movement. MOVE3D uses a published data base and a system of homogeneous scaling [4] to provide a mapping from the landmark targets to estimated muscle origins and insertions. The accuracy of the estimates have been evaluated [5] and three-dimensional computer graphics have been developed to illustrate the musculoskeletal kinematics. Figures 3 and 4 are examples of three-dimensional graphics displays for the right lower extremity during walking. Changes in position of the anatomical segments and the related changes in the muscle lines of action, illustrated by the solid lines, can be seen throughout the movement. This addition of muscle kinematics to the software allows a more complete picture of musculoskeletal motion.

All major components of MOVE3D, including the three-dimensional graphics, have been written by the author and their copyrights are maintained by NIH. This has enabled the software to be made available at no cost to research and clinical facilities worldwide. It is believed that the use of this software, both at NIH and at other facilities, will produce a better understanding of human motion and its control, leading to improvements in the treatment of people suffering from a variety of movement disorders.

References

- [1] T.M. Kepple, S.J. Stanhope, K.N. Lohmann, and N.R. Roman, "A Video-based technique for measuring ankle-subtalar motion during stance," *Journal of Biomedical Engineering*, Vol 12, pp. 273-280, 1990.
- [2] K.L. Siegel, S.J. Stanhope, and G.E. Caldwell, "Kinematic and kinetic adaptations in the lower limb during stance in gait of unilateral femoral neuropathy patients," *Submitted to Clinical Biomechanics*, December 1991.
- [3] P.G. O'Connell, K.L. Siegel, T.M. Kepple, S.J. Stanhope, Lohmann, and L.H. Gerber, "Gait in Rheumatoid Arthritis with Metatarsalgia," *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, Vol 72, pp. 776, 1990.
- [4] S.C. White, H.J. Yack, and D.A. Winter "A Three-dimensional musculoskeletal model for gait analysis. Anatomical Variability Estimates," *Journal of Biomechanics*, Vol 22, pp. 885-893, 1989.
- [5] T.M. Kepple, A.S. Arnold, and S.J. Stanhope, "The Estimation of Muscle Origins and Insertions in a 3D Motion Analysis and Graphics Program," *Proceedings of the International Symposium on 3-D Analysis of Human Motion*, Vol 1, pp. 119-122, 1991.

Figure 1. Graphic representation of a subject walking.

Figure 2. Ground reaction force vectors.

Figure 3. 3-D display of right lower extremity during stance.

Figure 4. 3-D display of right lower extremity during walking.